

15, St Johns Street,
Oxford.

11/2/72.

Dear Karl,

Thanks very much for your letter. Congratulations! you're a little young to be giving the Reckitt lecture--what will you do when you are 60?? That's ~~rather~~ rather a distinction. Thank you for your clearance on the Saudi material and for Fields address.

I've managed to complete ten pages of my thesis in the last three days. I'm eating drinking and sleeping it, so it is ploughing on.

I am writing a piece to include both Sirjan and DD. I've heard that I can include (inshallah!) a photo of DD. I suppose that the best one to illustrate is the DD room of pots (DD 4) that was in Iran IX on the grounds that not many people bother to read the reports on excavations, or do you think something else like the Celadon should go in ?? After long adventures the print ~~from~~ that was illustrated in Iran IX ended up with me in Iran-- but it is now being shipped on it's way back. Do you have another print available? or would something else be better? In any case if you could manage something (I'm supposed to produce it by mid March) I'd be most grateful.

Some ~~of~~ of the DD drawings are still undergoing surgery at Oxford because the sherds-- to be fair to the artist they are very difficult pieces, but it is just too hard for me to illustrate "flowing spirals" with drawings that make them look like sick zigzags! so I'm still playing with them. *will redraw.*

Did you get the whole ~~the~~ DD painted pot in the 1971 division? If you did I'd appreciate when you get a chance having it photographed together with the 1970 whole painted pot you have from DD 4 (In December it was on top of the large cabinet to the right of the lab as you go in the door, in splendour beside one of your fine Chinese neolithic pots). It would clearly be most economical in publication to have them both on the same print. (black and white and colour slide please)

Could you get at my expense a ~~hand~~ hand W and a colour slide of the 2 painted pots the Museum has from Istakhr (gift of the Boston Museum of Fine Arts). They are both in the Near Eastern Room. One is on display to the right of the door, the other is in case 9. Martha could easily find them, and if it is difficult to get a photo done she could easily take a snappy crappy shot for me. I'd half like to show a slide of them at the Oxford Congress if that is O.K. with you.

Best wishes to Marty and everyone at Harvard. *greetings* *ADL*